

FORMS, METHODS AND MEANS OF ORGANIZING ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION OF SCHOOLCHILDREN

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Annotation: The article analyzes the forms, methods and means of organizing the environmental education of schoolchildren

Keywords: story, explanation, conversation, work with a textbook and a book, observation, demonstration of visual aids, films and filmstrips, oral and written exercises, graphic and laboratory work.

Forms, methods and means of organizing environmental education are distinguished:

- a) traditional
- b) active, innovative.

Allocate:

- a lesson as a traditional form (introductory lessons, thematic lessons, lecture lessons, conversation lessons, etc.).

-special lessons (independent work of students, the method of educational discussions, role-playing games).

-extracurricular and extracurricular activities (research method, experiment, solving environmental problems).

- electives, lectures, storytelling, watching movies.

- various types of excursions.

-MASS MEDIA.

The most accepted is the classification of methods according to the source of knowledge (word, visual aids, practical activity). According to this approach, the methods can be grouped into three groups.

1. Verbal methods: story, explanation, conversation, work with a textbook and a book.

2. Visual methods: observation, demonstration of visual aids, films and filmstrips.

3. Practical methods: oral and written exercises, graphic and laboratory work.

The most effective means of environmental education is a variety of children's activities (educational, cognitive, artistic, creative, play). A special role is played by environmental protection activities of schoolchildren. Its types are varied:

- for the protection of the natural environment (feeding animals; rescuing animals in trouble; fighting garbage; making feeders and bird houses; installing signs in places where protected plants are distributed);

- for the prevention of bad deeds in nature and the fight against them (participation in the "green" and "blue" patrols, raids in nature);

- to improve the natural environment (planting plants, landscaping slopes, clearing the forest from dry wood);

- to promote and explain the ideas of nature conservation (conversations with comrades, parents, adults, making posters, publishing wall newspapers, preparing radio broadcasts);

- on the preservation and use of the aesthetic values of nature (collection of natural material, production of panels, handicrafts from natural material).

The main criterion for the effectiveness of the work on the formation of the ecological culture of schoolchildren is the unity of their ecological consciousness and behavior. Therefore, it is very important to strengthen in the minds of every student the understanding that man belongs to nature and his duty and duty to take care of it.

Success in environmental education and upbringing of younger schoolchildren largely depends on the extent to which the teacher stimulates interest, the desire to get to know the world around more deeply and improve in all types of environmental activities.

At the first stages in elementary school, the most appropriate methods are those that analyze and correct the ecological value orientations, interests and needs that have

developed among schoolchildren. Using children's experience of observations and environmental activities, the teacher in the course of a conversation with the help of facts, figures, judgments can cause emotional reactions in students, forms their personal attitude to the problem (Ignatieva 2005: 57).

At the stage of formation of an environmental problem, methods that stimulate independent activity of students acquire a special role. Tasks and tasks are aimed at identifying contradictions in the interaction between society and nature, at the formation of a problem and the birth of ideas about the way to solve it, taking into account the concept of the subject being studied. Discussions stimulate learning activities, contributing to the manifestation of students' personal attitude to problems, acquaintance with real local environmental conditions, and the search for ways to solve them (Derevyanko, Savelyeva, Babansky 1989: 40-44).

At the stage of theoretical substantiation of the methods of harmonic influence of society and nature, the teacher turns to the story, which allows presenting the scientific foundations of nature conservation in broad and versatile relationships, taking into account factors of the global, regional, local levels (Isaeva, 2000: 35-36).

In the new natural science courses, more attention is paid to such teaching methods as modeling environmental situations of moral choice, which summarize the experience of decision-making, form value orientations, develop the interests and needs of schoolchildren, a thought experiment, a natural history workshop, and work on environmental projects.

The need to express aesthetic feelings and experiences by creative means (drawing, story, poetry, etc.) is activated. Art makes it possible to compensate for the prevailing number of logical elements of knowledge. A synthetic approach to reality, characteristic of art, emotionality is especially important for the development of motives for studying and protecting nature (Postnikova 1991: 44-47).

Role-playing games are a means of psychological preparation of schoolchildren for real environmental situations. They are built taking into account the specific goals of the subject. The game in the educational process is life itself, a figurative model of life

situations, a projection on the natural process of the child's life. While playing, the child acquires a diverse experience of interaction with the outside world; performs quite specific environmental work; learns the rules of behavior in the environment; becomes kind, sensitive, responsive to someone else's misfortune. The game enriches the child's personal experience with examples of positive interaction with the environment. This is extremely important in the modern situation, which provides the child with an infinite number of negative examples. The game is interesting, captivating, the game is full of images and visualization that remain in children's memory (Saidakova 1993: 40-42).

In an effort to evoke emotional reactions in schoolchildren, to show the unattractiveness of irresponsible actions, the teacher uses an example and encouragement.

Punishment is an extreme, exceptional measure of influence on students. If these methods of education are used at the right stage of education, taking into account the psychological preparedness of students and taking into account natural conditions, then the teacher can form an environmentally literate and educated person (Tsvetkova 1994: 265).

Excursions and walks along the ecological path are of great educational and educational importance. The ecological trail is a type of "nature study trail" that has been actively created in recent years. The purpose of creating such a trail is to educate children on the example of specific natural objects, communicate with nature, and cultivate a caring attitude towards it. On walks along the ecological path, children are taught to capture a beautiful landscape, a lonely tree, and then, having come to a group, make a sketch and compose a story according to their own drawing. Great importance in the environmental education of children is given to conducting observations on a walk. This work not only develops children's observation skills, but also encourages them to draw conclusions about certain phenomena occurring in living and inanimate nature, developing the child's logical thinking and colloquial speech. Excursions along the ecological path bring great joy and pleasure to children; love for nature is laid here.

Love nature can only be one who knows and understands it, who knows how to see it. In order for a person to learn this, it is necessary to instill a love for nature from early childhood. When interacting with the environment, children's horizons expand, new knowledge is acquired, spiritual, moral and volitional qualities are brought up, such as friendship and mutual assistance, mutual trust, perseverance, endurance, collectivism. Motor skills are developed and health is strengthened, the rules of behavior in the surrounding natural and object world are studied. In order to form a conscious attitude towards nature in children, it is necessary to carefully use the natural and object environment, show the relationship of plants and animals with external conditions, their adaptability to the environment, the dependence of life and the state of the body on the impact of external facts, human activity.

Thus, properly planned work leads to the fact that children become kinder, able to empathize, rejoice, worry, master the skills of caring for plants and birds.

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